

D1.3 – Data Management Plan

**SYSAGE – Building Excellence in Systems Immunology and
Healthy Ageing research**

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SYSAGE

Building excellence in Systems Immunology and Healthy Ageing research

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
BAM	Binary Alignment Map
CC BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
CC0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DDI	Data documentation Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EHSOA	Estonian Health Services Organisation Act
EstBB	Estonian Biobank
FCS	Flow Cytometry Standard
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPL-3.0	GNU General Public License v3.0
HGRA	Human Genes Research Act
HIPC	Human Immunology Project Consortium
IP	Institut Pasteur
IT	Information technology
MI	Milieu Intérieur
MiFlowCyt	Minimum Information about a Flow Cytometry Experiment
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PBMC	Peripheral blood mononuclear cells
PC	Project Coordinator
PDF	Portable Document Format
PI	Principal investigator
PM	Project Manager
SAPU	Sensitive Data Analysis Platform
SAPU	Sensitive Data Analysis Platform
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
UTARTU	University of Tartu
VCF	Variant Call Format
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive Summary

Data Management Plan (DMP) is the comprehensive document that aims to describe the processes used in SysAge project as they relate to the data obtained, stored, backed up, secured and preserved long-term. The grant agreement of this project mandates the use of open access scientific publications.

The DMP will be updated throughout the duration of the project, at key project milestones (e.g., before major data collection phases and prior to submission of consortium publications). Updates will be recorded in the Document Version History. The first version of this document needs to be submitted by month 6 (February 2025) and second by month 17 (January 2026). This DMP can also be found on DMP online and will use the ERC template as well as Zenodo.

The SysAge project will follow FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and reusable) when it comes to data management. This document will cover how those principles will be achieved.

Project Summary

The aim of the SysAge project is to contribute to the identification of the novel molecular pathways that lead to accelerated decline of the immune system and age-related diseases, which will pave the way for the discovery of novel treatment targets. Within the pilot research UTARTU will take advantage of the recent COVID-19 vaccination campaigns and collected blood samples and data about vaccine response from 4000 Estonian Biobank donors (two thirds over 50 years of age) at two time points half a year apart. Mining of this dataset would lead to the identification of most important factors leading to poor vaccine responses. This would pave the way to building more effective vaccine strategies for older individuals in the future.

Finding prognostic biomarkers and novel treatment targets requires a detailed understanding of the changes that occur in the aging immune system, which can only be accomplished through longitudinal population cohort studies using a systems immunology approach. To achieve this, SysAge will build upon the knowledge base of the MI (Milieu Intérieur) consortium to learn the techniques and protocols that have proved to be most informative in dissecting the functional capacity of the immune system as a whole, to map the normal variability of the aging immune system and to discover the deviations associated with immune system decline as early as possible. The parameters for healthy adult population immune variability have been accumulating during recent years in IP (Institut Pasteur). The application of carefully harmonized protocols on the older individuals recruited during the current pilot research project would enable to estimate the feasibility of the selected approach to carry out a comprehensive longitudinal study on Estonian Biobank donors as a follow-up project.

1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

The SysAge project involves both secondary use of existing data and re-use of previously generated datasets. Existing Estonian Biobank (EstBB) COVID-19 vaccination data will be used. In addition, selected datasets from the MI project from IP are re-used for comparative analyses and validation of results generated.

The EstBB dataset contains info about donors (n= 4257), who have donated blood twice: in spring 2022 (n= 4270) and in autumn 2022 (n=3789). The database contains information about the IgG levels towards SARS-CoV2 Spike RBD in two timepoints, vaccination and infection history, electronic health data and prescription drug data and genotyping data.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Data type	Details about the data	Format	Size
Genotyping data	Re-used	vcf	150 GB
Electronic health data	Re-used	csv	1 GB
Prescription drug data	Re-used	csv	1 GB
SARS-Cov2 S RBD IgG data	Re-used	csv	<1 GB
Lifestyle data	Re-used/generated, questionnaires	csv	1 GB
Antibodies	Generated, experiments	csv	<1 GB
Spectral cytometry	Generated, experiments	fcs	20 TB
Cytokine production	Generated, experiments	csv	<1 GB
Clinical blood tests	Generated, laboratory	csv	<1 GB
Physical performance	Generated, test	csv	<1 GB
REDCap database	Re-used/ generated	csv	1 GB
MI data	Re-used	vcf, csv	
Software application source code	Re-used/ generated	R Markdown	<1 GB
Experimental protocols	generated	doc/pdf	<1 GB
Publications	open access	doc/pdf	<1 GB
Course curricula	generated	doc/pdf	<1 GB
Physical data	DNA, RNA, PBMCs, serum		

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

SysAge project will take advantage of the recent COVID-19 vaccination campaigns and collected blood samples and data about vaccine response from 4000 EstBB donors (two thirds over 50 years of age) at two time points half a year apart. Mining of this comprehensive dataset, under the guidance of IP, would lead to the identification of most important factors leading to poor vaccine responses. This would pave the way to building more effective vaccine strategies for older individuals in the future.

Finding prognostic biomarkers and novel treatment targets requires a detailed understanding of the changes that occur in the aging immune system, which can only be accomplished through longitudinal population cohort studies using systems immunology approach. To achieve this, we will build upon the knowledge base of the MI consortium to learn the techniques and protocols that have proved to be most informative in dissecting the functional capacity of the immune system as a whole, to map the normal variability of the aging immune system and to discover the deviations associated with immune system decline as early as possible. The parameters for healthy adult population immune variability have been accumulating during the recent years in IP. The application of carefully harmonized protocols on the older individuals recruited during the current pilot research project would enable to estimate the feasibility of the selected approach to carry out a comprehensive longitudinal study on EstBB donors as a follow-up project.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The approximate expected size of the data is included in the table above.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The SysAge project combines secondary use of data and biological materials collected during a previous COVID-19 vaccination response study in approximately 4,000 EstBB donors with newly generated pilot data collected during the SysAge project.

The re-used data originate from a study in which serum samples, PBMCs, and associated clinical and questionnaire data were collected to assess vaccine responses. These biological samples are currently stored in the institutional sample repository maintained by the Molecular Pathology Research group at the UTARTU and will be transferred to EstBB storage after the end of the SysAge project. During the earlier study, participant-level information and measurements from serum assays were stored in REDCap in

pseudonymised form. Clinical blood test results were generated by SYNLAB and transferred via a secure data transfer mechanism in a pseudonymised form directly into REDCap, using an infrastructure established during the previous project. In addition, EstBB-related registry data, including genotyping data, diagnoses, and prescription drug information originating from the Health and Welfare Information Systems Centre, are re-used in SysAge and stored and processed on secured University of Tartu High Performance Computing Centre servers under restricted access conditions.

During the SysAge project, new biological samples and experimental data will be generated within a pilot longitudinal research framework. These include additional serum samples, PBMCs, and whole-blood stimulation supernatants collected for antibody measurements, cytokine analyses, and immunophenotyping using spectral cytometry. Unlike the previous study, where pseudonymised laboratory and clinical data were transferred by SYNLAB into REDCap, the newly generated SysAge pilot data will be captured, governed, and stored within the EstBB environment. EstBB will perform pseudonymisation prior to researcher access, and participant-level data and associated metadata will be managed according to EstBB governance, access control, and long-term stewardship policies. Newly collected biological samples will be initially stored in the Molecular Pathology laboratory and transferred to EstBB premises by 2030.

All raw experimental data generated within SysAge are stored in dedicated experiment-specific folders that include references to the applicable Standard Operating Procedures (SOP), the identity of the experimenter, and the date of data generation. Processed and analysed data are maintained in master files with clear version numbers and update dates to ensure traceability. Questionnaire data and physical performance measurements are stored in the appropriate data capture environments, namely REDCap for the earlier study and the EstBB environment for the SysAge pilot.

To validate and contextualise selected findings from SysAge, relevant datasets generated within the MI project at IP will also be re-used under the applicable access conditions.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Data could be useful for scientist working in similar fields, particularly human immunology, immunosenescence, but also to spectral cytometry community. The discovered biomarkers may attract commercial interest. The developed course curricula may be useful for universities teaching medicine.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making Data findable, including provisions for metadata

The SysAge project aims to align all data and metadata from its work packages with the FAIR principles, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Both the consortium and the European Commission are interested in maximizing the value of the generated data beyond the project's duration. However, accessible does not necessarily mean unrestricted open access, we reserve the right to protect sensitive data. This includes personal data and potential confidential commercial information. To balance confidentiality with data sharing, anonymization techniques will be used where possible. For publicly shared data, the project will use common software, vocabularies, platforms and distribution channels to facilitate reuse in future projects.

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Wherever possible, we will deposit our data that is generated within the SysAge project in specialised repositories which provide persistent identifiers like DOI (Digital Object Identifier).

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created?

SysAge will provide detailed metadata for all newly generated datasets to enable discovery and reuse. The metadata provided include Descriptive metadata (Information on title, authors, date, description, format and keywords), administrative metadata (Project, funding, project period, grant number), experimental metadata (Details on experimental setups), sample metadata (Pseudonymized IDs, with cohort-specific details), analysis metadata (protocols for data analysis).

All metadata will be linked to datasets using DOIs.

What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?

SysAge will follow established metadata and data management standards. As the data generated within SysAge project are mostly associated with parameters of the immune system we'll follow the guidelines generated by Human Immunology Project Consortium (HIPC). Immune exposure is relevant for our data in the form of COVID-19 vaccination and infection. HIPC specifies a structured format (immune exposure model) to characterize human immune responses/mechanisms elicited by vaccinations,

adjuvants or natural infections. For the data from immune assays of biomarker discovery (ELISA, multiplexed bead-based assays) from serum samples or from cell stimulation supernatants in addition to results from the assayed biological samples we will submit the results from the control samples and their standard curves. Flow cytometry data will be accompanied by Minimum Information about a Flow Cytometry Experiment (MiFlowCyt) that establishes criteria for recording and reporting information about the flow cytometry experiment overview, samples, instrumentation and data analysis. Data collected by questionnaires will follow Data documentation Initiative (DDI) guidelines.

In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how?

For aspects of the project where formal standards may not exist, SysAge will develop custom metadata frameworks, including comprehensive descriptions of experimental protocols (e.g., reagent concentrations and stimulants used in whole blood cultures), file organization details and data processing steps (documented in README files), anonymization protocols to ensure participant confidentiality, in line with GDPR requirements.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

At least three carefully selected keywords will accompany each dataset to enhance discoverability. These keywords will be derived from standardized ontologies (e.g., MeSH) and will reflect SysAge's focus on healthy aging, vaccination response, inflammaging and immunosenescence.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

SysAge metadata will be designed to enable harvesting and indexing. Metadata will be published alongside datasets in repositories that support Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

2.2. Making data accessible

2.2.1. Repository

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

We will deposit our data only to trusted repositories like Zenodo, FlowRepository, OWEY. IP has generated its own data lake OWEY (<https://dataset.owey.io/doi>), that is able to assign DOI to datasets that will be generated in collaboration with UTARTU.

Repository mapping:

- Public/non-sensitive outputs (processed datasets, protocols) → Zenodo (DOI).
- Spectral cytometry raw FCS → FlowRepository (DOI)
- Sensitive individual-level genotype/transcriptome and clinical records → EstBB under controlled access; EstBB does not assign DOIs.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Yes. The SysAge project has adopted Zenodo as its primary public repository for non-sensitive datasets and has registered there as part of the EU Open Research Repository. Relevant project documents and have already been uploaded to Zenodo, and the consortium is familiar with its deposition procedures, licensing options, and DOI assignment mechanisms.

Arrangments with OWEY have also been made this is also needed to access MI data for verification of planned pilot study

DataDOI is free for the members of UTARTU and is having an excellent user support free of charge and will remain as an alternative option.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

We make sure that the data generated throughout the SysAge project will be stored in repositories which assign DOI.

2.2.2. Data

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Non-identifiable metadata and summary statistics will be made openly available to the community. Genetic and transcriptomic data, however, are in most cases considered as sensitive. Accordingly, these are identifiable data and will therefore be made available under restricted access only, in order to comply with National and European legislations.

UTARTU follows the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) by European Council and Estonian laws. The EstBB activity is regulated by special law regulations. These are Human Genes Research Act (HGRA) and Estonian Personal Data Protection Act and Estonian Health Services Organisation Act. There are also “Terms and conditions for storage of pseudonymised tissue samples, descriptions of DNA and descriptions of health condition of gene donors” and regulation on “Procedure for issuing tissue samples, descriptions of DNA and descriptions of health condition of gene donors” and on “Procedure for destroying the gene donor’s tissue sample, description of DNA, description of health condition and data which enables de-pseudonymisation” issued by the Ministry of Social Affairs.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

No fixed embargo period is foreseen beyond the time required for scientific publication. Data underlying publications will be made available at the time of article publication. In case of sensitive data, it will be released with restricted access.

An embargo may be applied where necessary to protect potential intellectual property (e.g. patent applications), in line with the GA (Grant Agreement)

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol? If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Non-sensitive data generated within the SysAge project will be made accessible through trusted public repositories, enabling open access to datasets, metadata, and research outputs that do not contain personal or sensitive information. These repositories provide persistent identifiers and standard download mechanisms, ensuring long-term accessibility and reuse both during and after the end of the project.

Access to sensitive and personal data is restricted in accordance with GDPR, national legislation, and the governance framework of the EstBB. Such data will not be released openly but will be made available under controlled access through the EstBB's established data access procedures. Approved researchers will analyse individual-level data within secure computing environments, including the Sensitive Data Analysis Platform provided by the University of Tartu High-Performance Computing Centre, which is designed to prevent unauthorised copying, transfer, or extraction of sensitive data.

This controlled access model applies both during the active phase of the SysAge project and after its completion, ensuring long-term but regulated access to sensitive datasets.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

The identity of individuals accessing sensitive data is ascertained through the formal access procedures of the EstBB, which require institutional authentication and documented approvals. Access is granted only to researchers who are explicitly listed in a valid ethics approval issued by the Research Ethics Committee of the Ministry of Social Affairs and whose research proposal has been approved by the scientific committee of the EstBB, which acts as the Data Access Committee for evaluating and authorising access to personal and sensitive data.

In addition, approved researchers are required to enter into a contractual agreement with the Estonian Genome Centre and to comply with the applicable terms of use. Each approved data access request requires the execution of a Data Use Agreement defining the scope of permitted data use, data protection obligations, and reporting requirements. These agreements and approval records are maintained by the EstBB and form part of its access governance both during the SysAge project and after its completion.

2.2.3. Metadata

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

All metadata generated within the SysAge project will be made openly available under a CC0 public domain dedication, in accordance with the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement. Domain-specific metadata standards, such as Data Documentation Initiative (DDI), Minimum Information about a Flow Cytometry Experiment (MiFlowCyt), and Human Immunology Project Consortium (HIPC) guidelines, will be used to describe experimental, immunological, and cohort-specific information.

Repository-level metadata will follow the Dublin Core standard to support interoperability, harvesting, and indexing by external services.

For datasets that are not freely accessible due to legal or ethical restrictions, the openly available metadata will include clear information on access conditions and instructions on how to apply for controlled access through the relevant data access procedures.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Sensitive individual-level data will be preserved within the EstBB database under its long-term stewardship and controlled-access governance.

Non-sensitive datasets and domain-specific subsets suitable for public sharing, such as spectral cytometry data, will be deposited in certified repositories that support long-term preservation and persistent identifiers, ensuring they remain findable and citable over time.

Raw experimental data and intermediate analysis files that are not deposited in public repositories due to size, sensitivity, or lack of a suitable domain repository will be stored on secure UTARTU servers for a minimum of 15 years in accordance with institutional retention practices.

Metadata will remain openly available even if the underlying data are no longer accessible. Metadata will be deposited alongside datasets in certified repositories that support long-term preservation and indexing, and will follow the Dublin Core standard (supplemented where relevant by domain-specific standards), ensuring metadata remain machine-readable, interoperable, and accessible, including clear information on access conditions for controlled datasets.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes. Documentation describing the software required to access, read, and interpret the data and metadata will be provided alongside each dataset. This documentation will include information on file formats, required software tools, software versions, and any dependencies needed for data access or analysis, and will be included in dataset-specific README files or metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Data are provided in interoperable, open formats such as VCF, CSV, FCS, and BAM. Design files necessary for data analysis will be made publicly available alongside the uploaded files in the relevant repositories.

Controlled vocabularies and ontologies (e.g. MeSH, Gene Ontology) are used where applicable.

Internally, experiments are conducted following detailed protocols maintained in Electronic Lab Notebooks by the experimenters. Standard experimental protocols will be referenced and linked in dataset-specific README files. These protocols are prepared in Word and saved as PDFs, ensuring they include all necessary details to replicate the experiment and track individual samples. The information in the notebooks corresponds with data collected on the same date, allowing experiments to be reproduced by following the protocols.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Not applicable.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

When applicable, we will refer to previous datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

In principle, all experimental analyses and data will remain re-usable for reanalysis. To prevent that data have been acquired in a format that depends on a specific software that might not be usable anymore, we aim to save all useful raw data in a format that is open access proof.

For example:

- .csv for all standard data with values
- .csv or .fcs for flow cytometry data,

A readme file will be provided for each dataset with a summary of the methodology used for analyses and quality control. Code associated with analysis will be deposited on a dedicated GitHub page referenced in the associated publication and in the repository and where relevant, software environments and package versions will be documented to support reproducibility.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Non-sensitive data generated within the SysAge project will be made openly available to permit the widest possible reuse, while ensuring that no individual can be identified. These datasets will be shared under a standard open reuse licence, specifically the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) licence, which allows reuse, redistribution, and adaptation with appropriate attribution to the data creators. All software code developed within the SysAge project and shared via GitHub will be released under an open-source licence GPL-3.0 (GNU General Public License v3.0). Metadata associated with all datasets will be released under a CC0 (Creative Commons Zero) public domain dedication, in line with the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

Genotyping data, RNA sequencing data, and other individual-level health data are considered sensitive, as they can potentially lead to the identification of individuals. Such data will therefore not be made openly available and will be shared only under controlled access conditions. Access to sensitive data will be granted upon request through established EstBB procedures and analyses will be conducted within secure environments, such as the Sensitive Data Analysis Platform (SAPU), in compliance with GDPR, national legislation, and the informed consent provided by study participants.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

All the data generated during the SysAge project will be stored in trusted repositories and containing sufficient amount of metadata. This would secure the usability of the data after the end of the project. The only concern is currently the FlowRepository as the community has faced problems with downloading data from this repository. We will keep this in mind and consider alternative repositories: Immport and dataDOI.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Dedicated and secured research folder structure for all research data will be generated. For each analysis, the raw data (in an acceptable open format e.g. .fcs/.csv/), and all the files that belong to the experiments and the analyses thereof (including pdf of the lab-journal) will be stored in the raw data directory for each experiment. Also, the metadata of that experiment, including the exact methods/layout of the experiment will be stored in the same folder. This folder will have a specific number and a title. Modifications or updates to these analysis files are tracked using an appended version number at the end of the filename. Combined data analysis files for final publication figures are maintained in separate directories, as they are linked to data from several different experiments performed on different dates. Within the final data analysis directories, there will be a text file containing metadata regarding exactly which source (raw) data is contained within the analysis file, and the directory in which the raw data can be found.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

To ensure the integrity and reliability of the data collected and used throughout this project, we will implement several data quality assurance processes. These processes are designed to minimize errors, ensure consistency, and maintain data accuracy.

1. **Data Validation:** All data entered our systems will be checked for format and range validity to prevent incorrect data entry. Ensuring that data is correctly typed (e.g., numeric, text) to prevent type mismatches.
2. **Data Verification:** Data sources will be verified to ensure they are credible and reliable. Where possible, data will be cross-checked against other sources to confirm accuracy.
3. **Data Cleaning:** Regular checks will be performed to identify and correct errors in the data. Data will be standardized to ensure consistency across different datasets.
4. **Data Security:** Access to data will be restricted to authorized personnel only, using secure login credentials. Sensitive data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest to protect against unauthorized access.
5. **Backup and Recovery:** Daily incremental backups and regularly scheduled full backups managed by UTARTU central IT services.”
6. **Documentation and Monitoring:** All data quality processes will be thoroughly documented, including any changes made to the data. Continuous monitoring will be performed to ensure that data quality standards are met throughout the project lifecycle.

By implementing these data quality assurance processes, we aim to maintain high standards of data integrity, reliability, and security, ensuring that our research outcomes are based on accurate and trustworthy data.

3. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

All costs associated with the data collection, data storage and repository maintenance are covered by the SysAge WP1 budget.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Overall responsibility for data management lies with the PC (Project Coordinator) and PI (Principal Investigator). Day-to-day implementation of data management practices is supported by PM (Project Manager) and WPL (Work Package Leader) and institutional IT and data management services.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Long-term preservation of data generated within the SysAge project will be ensured through a combination of institutional infrastructures, biobank governance, and trusted repositories.

Sensitive individual-level data will be transferred to and governed by the EstBB database, where they are preserved for an unlimited period in accordance with national legislation, biobank policies, and participant consent. Decisions regarding long-term retention and access to these data are made within the EstBB governance framework, including its scientific committee and data access procedures.

Data that are not sensitive and that are suitable for broader reuse will be preserved using the secure data storage and backup infrastructure provided by the University of Tartu IT services. These data, including raw experimental files and intermediate analysis outputs that cannot be deposited in public repositories, will be stored on University of Tartu servers for a minimum of 15 years, in line with institutional data retention policies and supported by professional IT maintenance, regular backups, and access control mechanisms.

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Where appropriate, non-sensitive datasets, processed results, protocols, and software will also be deposited in trusted public repositories to ensure long-term findability and reuse.

4. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Comprehensive technical and organisational measures are in place to ensure the security of all data generated and used within the SysAge project, covering confidentiality, integrity, availability, and resilience of data and systems.

Biological samples and associated data are pseudonymised before reaching the laboratory, ensuring that project researchers do not have access to directly identifying information. Each sample is assigned an internal code, while the corresponding coding key is retained separately within secure systems managed by the EstBB or, for legacy data, within controlled REDCap environments. Access to participant-identifying information is strictly limited to authorised personnel and governed by institutional and biobank policies.

All raw and analysed data files are stored on secure University of Tartu servers that are maintained by professional IT personnel in accordance with institutional IT security and data protection policies. These servers are protected through role-based access control, institutional authentication mechanisms, and continuous system monitoring. Data stored on University of Tartu servers are backed up regularly as part of the central IT services: incremental backups are performed on a daily basis, while full backups are carried out at regular intervals, enabling reliable recovery in the event of accidental data loss, hardware failure, or security incidents. Backup copies are stored in physically and logically separate locations to reduce the risk of data loss, and backup procedures are periodically reviewed and tested by IT services to ensure their effectiveness.

Secure data transfer mechanisms are used whenever sensitive data are exchanged between systems or partners. Clinical laboratory data generated by certified laboratories are transferred in pseudonymised form using institution-approved secure data transfer channels. Access to sensitive datasets is logged, and records of data access, modification, and removal are maintained to ensure traceability and auditability. Procedures are in place for detecting, reporting, and responding to suspected security breaches, including corrective actions where required. In addition, University of Tartu staff involved in the SysAge project receive ongoing training and guidance related to information security and cyber hygiene, ensuring that data protection measures are consistently applied throughout the project lifecycle.

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Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes.

5. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

The SysAge project is subject to ethical and legal requirements related to the processing and sharing of personal and sensitive data, in particular genetic and health-related information. The University of Tartu complies with the GDPR and applicable Estonian legislation. The activities of the EstBB are regulated by specific national laws, including the Human Genes Research Act, the Estonian Personal Data Protection Act, and the Estonian Health Services Organisation Act, as well as by regulations issued by the Ministry of Social Affairs governing the storage, use, release, and destruction of pseudonymised tissue samples, DNA data, and health-related information of gene donors.

All participants of the EstBB have provided informed consent allowing the storage and scientific use of their data and biological material. The research activities proposed within the SysAge project, including the reuse of existing biobank data, data preservation, and the sharing of summary-level statistics, have been approved by the Estonian Committee on Bioethics and Human Research (approval nr. 1.1-12/4567). In addition, the pilot longitudinal research component of the project has received ethical approval from the same committee (decision of the Estonian Committee on Bioethics and Human Research, 14 November 2025, nr 1.1-12/3147).

Genetic and other individual-level health data are considered sensitive, and their sharing is therefore subject to strict restrictions. Access to such data is granted only to researchers who are explicitly listed in the relevant ethics approvals, have obtained approval from the scientific committee of the Estonian Genome Centre, and have signed the required contractual agreements and terms of use. Data sharing involving genetic data is conducted exclusively under controlled access conditions, in full compliance with national and European data protection legislation and the informed consent provided by study participants.

Potential ethical and legal issues related to intellectual property and commercialisation are also considered. The project works closely with the University of Tartu technology transfer office to ensure that research results and data with potential commercial value are treated as confidential until appropriate intellectual property protection measures, such as patent applications, are in place. Intellectual property rights, data ownership, and exploitation rules are defined in the consortium agreement and are aligned with the ethical principles and data sharing obligations of the project.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

The EstBB personal information data has no time limit. The data and material that is delivered to EstBB after the end of the project will be securely stored. The data that remain to Molecular pathology laboratory will be anonymised according to the dates set by the ethical applications.

6. Other Issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Not applicable.